

Synthesis, characterization and ion exchange behavior of a new four components cation exchanger based on Sn^{IV}

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Abstract : Present paper describes a new method for synthesis of tin(IV) iodotungstosilicate (TITS) exchanger. Ion exchange capacity (IEC) of the exchanger is found to be 0.86 meq/g for Na⁺, possesses good stability against high temperature upto 600 °C and chemicals of different strengths. IEC is determined for different metal ions, distribution studies are done and K_d values are calculated. The exchanger is selective for lead ions as shown by K_d value (176.78). IR of the compound indicates all the four expected components. XRD and SEM show that exchanger is in amorphous form. The synthesized material is useful in separation, water softening and water decontamination.

Keywords : Inorganic exchanger, exchange capacity, stability, K_d value.

Introduction

Present work includes study of a four components cation exchanger, its stability against temperature and radiations. Though a numbers of cation exchangers¹⁻⁷ have been reported but there is always a scope of new exchanger. The advantage of inorganic exchanger over organic exchanger⁸⁻¹⁰ also creates an attraction towards them. So a new four components inorganic exchanger is synthesized and characterized. Hit and trial method was used to find better exchanger by mixing the different salt solutions in different ratios.

The contamination of groundwater, which is a principal source of water, is a serious health and environmental problem all over the world. Pollution of ground water due to industrial effluent and municipal waste is a major concern in many cities and clusters in India. Contamination of water by heavy metals through the discharge of industrial waste water is a very serious environmental problem. Among the various heavy metals, lead(II) is a well known toxic metal ion which can be introduced to liquid wastes from the manufacturing processes of storage batteries, smelting and refining of lead, inks, paints and from the processes of mining. The elevated level of lead (>0.05 mg/L) and other heavy metals in the local water stream is a major concern to public. It has been desired that their concentration levels be reduced in in-

dustrial and municipal effluents before discharge into the water streams.

Various methods such as chemical precipitation, solvent extraction, ultra filtration, reverse osmosis, adsorption and ion exchange have been employed for the removal of lead and other toxic metal ions from water. Among the various methods employed for the removal of toxic metal ions, the ion exchange method has drawn the attention of researchers because of its selectivity and high efficiency of sorption from liquid media.

Synthesized ion exchanger was characterized on the basis of different studies such as IEC determination, thermal stability, chemical stability, distribution studies, IR, XRD and SEM. The selectivity of the exchanger for a metal ion was found on the bases of K_d values¹¹⁻¹⁵.

Experimental

Apparatus and chemicals used :

Two pan balance, Electronic balance (Samson model 300D), Magnetic stirrer with hot plate, oven (NSW India), Rotary Shaker (TANCO), Muffle furnace (SHIVAKI-T701 TANCO), Toshniwal research pH meter (model-110) and Borosil glasswares were used. Thermonicolet IR Spectrophotometer for IR, Philip Analytical X-ray, B.V. Diffractometer for XRD and FEI Quanta 200F for SEM were used.

All the chemicals and reagents used were analytical grade (AR). Stannic chloride pentahydrate (0.1 M), potassium iodate (0.1 M), sodium tungstate (0.1 M), sodiummetasilicate (0.1 M), etc. were used in synthesis of exchanger.

Synthesis of matrices :

Solutions of strength 0.1 M were used for synthesis of the matrix at RT (25 °C). Stannic chloride pentahydrate, potassium iodate, sodiummetasilicate and sodium tungstate solutions were intermixed, which gave white precipitate. Intermixing of the solutions was done in ten different ratios (Table 1). After intermixing pH adjusted to using 1 M HCl and left for 24 h at room temperature. Settled down precipitates were filtered and washed with distilled water, kept on the marked watch glasses, placed in an oven at 40 °C for 24 h and dried. Granulization was performed by cracking for increasing their surface area of dry matrices with hot distilled water and again dried at 40 °C for 24 h.

Table 1. Solution intermixing

Sr. no.	Sample no.	Stannic chloride solution (0.1 M)	Potassium iodate solution (0.1 M)	Sodium tungstate solution (0.1 M)	Sodiummetasilicate solution (0.1 M)
1.	TITS 1	1	1	1	1
2.	TITS 2 ^a	1	2	1	1
3.	TITS 3 ^b	1	1	2	1
4.	TITS 4 ^b	1	1	1	2
5.	TITS 5	2	1	1	1
6.	TITS 6	2	2	1	1
7.	TITS 7	2	1	2	1
8.	TITS 8	2	1	1	2
9.	TITS 9	3	2	2	1
10.	TITS 10	3	1	2	2

where TITS = Tin(IV) iododisilicotungstate; 1 = 50 mL, 2 = 100 mL, 3 = 150 mL. ^aPenetrate. ^bFormed insufficient precipitate.

Generation :

The granules were generated by putting 0.5 g matrices in 50 mL solution of 1 M HNO₃ solution. The process was repeated three times then left the samples as such in solution for 24 h. Then filtered and washed each charged matrix with distilled water till the extra acid present in matrix was removed. Then each charged matrix was dried in different marked watch glasses at 40 °C, thus they were converted to the H⁺-form.

Fig. 1. Relation between temperature and wt. loss (%).

Characterization :

IEC determination by column method :

The ion-exchange capacity was determined as usual by the column technique¹⁶⁻²⁰. Half gram of dry exchanger in H⁺ form was loaded in a column with glass wool support at the base. Sodium nitrate (1 M) solution was used to elute H⁺ ions completely from the exchanger column at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. The liberated H⁺ ions were determined titrimetrically using standardized sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 M). Weighed 500 mg of each dry sample and placed in seven different columns. NaNO₃ solution (1 M) was prepared and kept in each column and allowed to pass through exchanger. The solution was passed continuously till the pH of the effluent became the same as pH of the NaNO₃ solution. Effluent was titrated with standardized NaOH solution and IEC was calculated by following expression,

$$\text{IEC} = \frac{\text{Molarity of NaOH} \times \text{Used volume of NaOH}}{\text{Weight of exchanger}}$$

The sample 10 has maximum IEC i.e. 0.86 meq/g for Na⁺ (Table 2). On the basis on ion exchange capacity, this sample was selected for the bulk synthesis and detailed study was made. IEC was again determined by bulk materials.

Table 2. IEC determination of matrices

Sr. no.	Sample no.	Colour	Weight of ppt. (g)	IEC (meq/g)
1.	TITS 1	White	0.28	0.29
2.	TITS 5	White	2.45	0.36
3.	TITS 6	White	1.80	0.42
4.	TITS 7	White	1.85	0.39
5.	TITS 8	White	1.95	0.45
6.	TITS 9	White	3.12	0.51
7.	TITS 10	White	3.05	0.86

Fig. 2. pH titration graph.

Thermal stability :

To study the thermal stability of the exchanger, seven equal portions (500 mg) of the exchanger were heated at different temperature ranging from room temperature (25 °C) upto 600 °C in a muffle furnace separately for 60 min. Weight loss, change in IEC, and change in color of all the samples were recorded as shown in Table 3.

Chemical stability :

Chemical stability of the exchanger was also studied against different chemicals of different strengths. Weight loss and change in IEC of the exchanger in twelve solutions of different strengths were observed. In each twelve samples 0.5 g exchanger was placed in 50 mL of solution in conical flask and left them for 24 h at room tempera-

ture (25 °C). The next day filtered all the samples with Whatman filter paper and washed with distilled water till pH became neutral of effluent water then dried each samples at 40 °C. After drying weight loss and IEC was calculated of each sample (Table 4).

IEC determination for other metal ions :

Ion exchange capacity of the exchanger was also determined for five others block metals ions other than Na⁺. Weighed 500 mg of exchanger and placed in six different columns. Metal ion solution (1 M) was prepared and kept in each column and allowed to pass through exchanger. The solution was passed continuously till the pH of the effluent became the same as pH of the each metal ion solution. Effluent was titrated with standardized NaOH solution and IEC was calculated. A simple relation between IEC and hydrated radii was also be established (Table 5).

pH titration :

IEC of the synthesized exchanger in bulk was also determined by pH titration method. In this method eleven equal portion of the exchanger were placed in eleven solutions of equal volume containing sodium chloride (0.1 M) and sodium hydroxide (0.1 M) solution in eleven different volume ratios as given in Table 6.

All the solutions were intermittently shaken and then kept as such for 24 h. pH of each solution was determined by using pH meter. A graph was plotted between pH and hydroxide ions concentration. IEC was calculated from graph.

Distribution studies :

Distribution studies of the exchanger with six metal

Table 3 Thermal stability expression

Sr. no.	Temp. (°C)	W.O.E.B.H. (mg)	W.O.E.A.H. (mg)	Weight loss (mg)	C.O.E.B.H.	C.O.E.A.H.	IEC (meq/g)
1.	R.T.	500	500	0	White	White	0.86
2.	100	500	490	10	White	Brownish white	0.83
3.	200	500	480	20	White	Brown	0.77
4.	300	500	450	50	White	Brown	0.64
5.	400	500	440	60	White	Yellowish brown	0.59
6.	500	500	420	80	White	Yellowish brown	0.43
7.	600	500	410	90	White	Dark brown	0.36

where, W.O.E.B.H. = Weight of exchanger before heating, W.O.E.A.H. = Weight of exchanger after heating, C.O.E.B.H. = Colour of exchanger before heating, C.O.E.A.H. = Colour of exchanger after heating.

Fig. 3. IR spectrum of the TITS compound.

Table 4. Chemical stability table

Sr. no.	Chemicals	W.O.E.B.T. (mg)	W.O.E.A.T. (mg)	IEC (meq/g)
1.	D.W.	500	500	0.86
2.	HCl 1 N	500	490	0.81
3.	HCl 2 N	500	480	0.71
4.	HNO ₃ 1 N	500	490	0.68
5.	HNO ₃ 2 N	500	480	0.54
6.	H ₂ SO ₄ 1 N	500	500	0.65
7.	H ₂ SO ₄ 2 N	500	490	0.43
8.	HCOOH 2 N	500	500	0.49
9.	CH ₃ COOH 2 N	500	490	0.80
10.	NaOH 1 N	500	-	-
11.	NaOH 2 N	500	-	-
12.	KOH 2 N	500	-	-

(-) indicate complete dissolved of exchanger.

Table 5. IEC with different metal ions

Sr. no.	Metal ion	Compound	Hydrated radii	IEC (meq/g)
1.	Li ⁺	LiCl	10.0	0.44
2.	Na ⁺	NaCl	7.90	0.86
3.	K ⁺	KBr	5.30	0.88
4.	Mg ²⁺	MgCl ₂	10.80	0.38
5.	Ca ²⁺	CaCl ₂	9.60	0.46
6.	Ba ²⁺	BaCl ₂	8.80	0.49

ions were done by batch process. The exchanger was treated with the metal ion solution. Complexometric titrations with 0.1 M EDTA solution were performed to

Table 6. pH titration table

Sr. no.	Sample no.	Volume of NaOH (0.1 M) solution (mL)	Volume of NaCl (0.1 M) solution (mL)	Exchanger taken (g)	pH
1.	1	0	50	0.50	2.50
2.	2	5	45	0.50	7.28
3.	3	10	40	0.50	9.30
4.	4	15	35	0.50	10.28
5.	5	20	30	0.50	10.98
6.	6	25	25	0.50	11.47
7.	7	30	20	0.50	11.74
8.	8	35	15	0.50	11.88
9.	9	40	10	0.50	12.06
10.	10	45	5	0.50	12.16
11.	11	50	0	0.50	12.24

find the metal ion concentration in their solution before and after treatment with exchanger. The value so obtained was used to calculate K_d values for all the six metals by following expression (Table 7).

$$K_d = \frac{(I - F) \times V}{F \times W}$$

where I = Initial value of EDTA, F = Final value of EDTA, V = Volume taken, W = Weight of exchanger.

Results and discussion

Material characterization :

The IR spectra of the exchanger shows a strong and

Table 7. K_d value determination

Sr. no.	Metal ion (0.1 M)	Salt	Used volume of EDTA		K_d value
			B.T.	A.T.	
1.	Th ³⁺	Thorium sulphate	26.6	26.4	0.38
2.	Pb ²⁺	Lead nitrate	25.4	5.6	176.78
3.	Zn ²⁺	Zinc sulphate	26.6	24.4	4.51
4.	Cd ²⁺	Cadmium chloride	22.4	18.5	10.54
5.	Cu ²⁺	Copper sulphate	5.2	25.0	3.48
6.	Mg ²⁺	Magnesium chloride	26.1	24.4	0.48

where, B.T. = Before treatment, A.T. = After treatment.

broad band in the region of 3600–3000 cm^{-1} may be assigned to interstitial water molecule and -OH group. Another strong and sharp peak with maximum at 1627 cm^{-1} may be due to H–O–H bonding. The spectrum also shows a strong band in the region of 1550–1300 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of metal oxide. The peaks at

Fig. 4 SEM images of TITS.

567.85, 950.39 and 1471.8 indicate the presence of iodate, silicate and tungstate respectively (Fig. 3). IR proved the presence of all expected four components in the material.

X-Ray pattern of the exchanger was also found from IIT Roorkee, where Philip Analytical X-Ray D. V. Diffractometer was available. The diffraction pattern was exhibited by Fig. 5 which shown a number of peaks. X-Ray diffraction pattern of material in H⁺ form reveals the fact that the exchanger is amorphous in nature with weak peaks with weak intensities.

The SEM images of the exchanger had given in the range of 1.0 μm and 200.0 μm by FEI Quanta 200F shown in Fig. 4.

Different amount of precipitates in different volume ratio were obtained. Though the weight of sample-9 was maximum yet its ion exchange capacity was found low. Therefore sample-10 had shown good amount and maximum ion exchange capacity therefore selected for further study.

IEC determined by two methods i.e. column method and pH titration method were nearly same.

The relation between IEC and hydrated ionic radii exhibits that IEC decreases with increase in hydrated radii of the cation.

Thermal stability study revealed that the exchanger remain almost its IEC upto 100 °C. The exchanger shows IEC even 600 °C. In chemical stability study it was found that the exchanger does not lose IEC in distilled water. While in 2 N H₂SO₄ and HCl insignificant loss was noted.

Fig. 5. X-Ray diffraction of TITS.

The exchanger was completely dissolved in alkaline solutions. Stability against different chemicals was found satisfactory.

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